

Agenda for Future Research

Inclusive and Sustainable Food Systems

The ACCTING project explores the impact of Green Deal policies on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate and mitigate potential negative effects.

Its Agenda for Future Research highlights key research gaps across Green Deal policy areas and provides a clear overview of research priorities and needs for a fair and sustainable transition. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the development of future research agendas and pave the way for inclusive and effective policymaking and implementation.

The full set of research agendas covering other thematic areas can be found [on the ACCTING project website](#).

ACCTING Findings

- Participation in BUIs (Bottom-Up Initiatives) is related to behavioural changes in food values and consumption. Specifically, participants took more into consideration health and environmental (animal) welfare when choosing their food and reported higher consumption of plant-based and locally produced food. BUIs are also important for fostering community engagement and solidarity, as they offer a platform for individuals to connect, share resources, and promote collective goals for sustainability. This engagement strengthens social networks and enhances feelings of empowerment and belonging within the community. Despite their potential, BUIs struggle to reach socially vulnerable groups effectively, as they predominantly attract middle and upper-middle-class participants. Resistance among marginalised groups often arises from structural inequalities, creating challenges for BUIs to reach all vulnerable populations effectively. For instance, historical distrust and socioeconomic vulnerabilities prevent equitable access to community initiatives.
- Affordability and accessibility are crucial challenges that hinder the ability of socially vulnerable groups to adopt more sustainable food practices. Financial constraints make it difficult for these groups to access healthier, locally produced, or plant-based foods, which are often perceived as more expensive compared to conventional options. Systemic inequalities, such as poor access to food distribution networks and limited economic resources, exacerbate these challenges. These systemic barriers often prevent marginalised populations from reaping the benefits of sustainability initiatives, as they may be excluded from the opportunities offered by BUIs due to factors like cost, time, and social capital.
- Motherhood emerges as a powerful motivator for sustainable food choices, as mothers often feel a strong sense of responsibility for their children's health and well-being. This concern for their children's future drives many mothers to make more environmentally conscious and health-oriented food decisions, even in the face of time constraints. Feminist ideologies also play a significant role in empowering women to take an active role in the ecological movement. Women involved in BUIs or community-driven sustainability projects often gain confidence and agency, which is enhanced by the solidarity they experience within their communities. This empowerment is crucial for fostering long-term behavioural changes that promote sustainability at both the individual and collective levels.
- Community networks and social capital play a central role in supporting the success of BUIs. As seen in the case studies, individuals who are part of supportive social networks are more likely to engage in sustainable food behaviours and participate in BUIs.

- Community gardens (CGs) have emerged as vital community spaces that promote social cohesion, environmental sustainability, and food security, particularly for vulnerable groups. ACCTING's Pilot projects have demonstrated how digital platforms can enhance knowledge exchange, collaboration, and resource sharing among CG participants. CGs contribute to urban development by addressing intersectional inequalities and offering ecosystem services, such as urban cooling, biodiversity enhancement, and stormwater management. Yet, these benefits are often underacknowledged.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Role of Bottom-Up Initiatives in Sustainable Food Systems

While BUIs have shown promise in changing food behaviours, limited research exists on how these initiatives can be adapted and scaled to suit diverse socio-economic and geographical contexts. The current focus predominantly on urban and peri-urban areas leaves a gap in understanding how BUIs may be applied to rural food systems, where challenges may differ in terms of access, infrastructure, and resources.

Research questions

- How do bottom-up initiatives (BUIs) facilitate transformative sustainable food behavioural changes among the most vulnerable communities, and how do these behaviours intersect with broader socio-economic and cultural contexts that condition these processes?
- What structural, institutional, and contextual factors enable or constrain the scalability and sustainability of BUIs across diverse rural and urban landscapes, and how do these dynamics vary across different socio-political environments?

Subtheme 2. Inclusivity in Sustainable Food Movements

Although BUIs have great potential, their accessibility to socially vulnerable groups remains limited. Further research is needed to explore how initiatives can better integrate vulnerable populations, particularly those who are most at risk of food insecurity and environmental degradation. This research should also focus on gender+ considerations, with the goal of fostering inclusivity and challenging existing power structures within the food system.

Research questions

- What strategies can improve the inclusion of socially vulnerable groups in sustainable food movements?
- How can gender+ considerations be operationalized in food system initiatives to challenge entrenched power dynamics and promote transformative equity across all levels of the supply chain?
- What innovative communication models can leverage behavioural insights and cultural specificity to engage low-income and the most socially vulnerable populations in co-creating sustainable food systems?

Subtheme 3. Technological Interventions for Sustainable Food Systems

Digital tools and technologies offer a new avenue for empowering marginalised groups in food systems. However, limited exploration has been done on how these technologies can promote inclusivity and bridge the gap between food producers and consumers. There is also a need to assess whether low-tech solutions can provide viable alternatives that are more accessible and scalable in marginalised or resource-poor communities.

Research questions

- How can emerging digital tools and platforms be strategically designed and implemented to foster equitable connections between food producers and vulnerable consumer groups, addressing issues of accessibility, affordability, and trust?
- What socio-technical, economic, and cultural factors influence the adoption and sustained use of digital agriculture technologies among the most vulnerable populations, and how can these be leveraged to create inclusive and resilient agricultural systems?
- How do low-tech solutions contribute to inclusivity and equal access to sustainable food systems? Could low-tech solutions offer scalable, cost-effective ways to support sustainability initiatives, especially in marginalised or resource-poor communities?

Subtheme 4. Rural Food Systems and Intersectional Vulnerabilities

Rural communities face unique challenges in adopting sustainable practices due to their geographical isolation, lack of infrastructure, and lower access to resources. More research is needed to understand the intersectional vulnerabilities faced by rural populations and how tailored approaches can be developed to enhance their resilience and food security.

Research question

- How do rural-specific vulnerabilities impact the adoption of sustainable practices, and what tailored approaches can be developed to enhance resilience and food security in these communities?

Subtheme 5. Measuring Impact and Adaptability

Gender+ perspectives remain underrepresented in food system research and initiatives, and innovative methodologies are needed to assess the effectiveness of BUIs and other sustainability initiatives. Future research should focus on developing tools that can measure the long-term impact of these initiatives, particularly in terms of food equity and gender equality.

Research questions

- What innovative methodologies can be developed to measure the impacts of BUIs on food equity?
- How can BUIs be made resilient to changing environmental, economic, and political conditions?

Subtheme 6. Political and Structural Barriers in Sustainable Food Systems

Political ideologies play a significant role in shaping sustainability efforts, often creating structural barriers that hinder or support environmentally sustainable practices. Political choices can determine which policies are enacted and how sustainability initiatives are implemented, affecting their accessibility to vulnerable populations.

Research questions

- Does political ideation create structural barriers related to environmental sustainability in modern societies? How do different political perspectives influence the accessibility and adoption of sustainable food practices in vulnerable communities?
- How can food waste practices in vulnerable communities contribute to accelerating environmental sustainability? Could food waste reduction be integrated into local food systems to create environmental, economic, and social benefits, especially for marginalised populations?

Subtheme 7. The Role of Fatherhood and Activism in Sustainable Food and Mobility Choices

The dynamics of family structures and caregiving roles, especially in relation to fatherhood and parenthood, are underexplored in terms of their influence on sustainable food practices. Fatherhood could play a significant role in motivating more sustainable food choices, particularly when it comes to concerns for children's health and the future. Additionally, activism in sustainable mobility has traditionally been associated with women, and more inclusive approaches are needed to engage men in sustainable transport initiatives.

Research questions

- How can fatherhood (parenthood) be leveraged as a driver for behavioural change in adopting sustainable food practices? Could fathers' concerns for their children's health and the future play a role in shifting their food behaviours?
- Activism in sustainable mobility tends to be more associated with women than men. Could more inclusive activism approaches be developed that engage men in promoting sustainable transport practices, addressing gender disparities in eco-activism and mobility?

Subtheme 8. Indigenous Knowledge in Sustainable Food Systems

Indigenous knowledge plays a crucial role in fostering sustainable food systems. These communities have long practiced methods of environmental stewardship that align with the principles of sustainability, and these practices offer valuable insights into building more resilient food systems. The integration of indigenous knowledge can contribute to creating culturally sensitive and inclusive sustainability frameworks.

Research question

- How can indigenous knowledge be more fully integrated into sustainability research and practices, especially in relation to food systems, to promote a deeper understanding of environmental stewardship within marginalised communities?

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

As the project approaches its conclusion in May 2025, the research team has developed a Research Agenda outlining key knowledge gaps across Green Deal policy areas. This document serves as a valuable reference for future research and policymaking.

Discover the [Research Agenda published during the first research cycle](#).

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